

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EXPLORING DIGITAL ISSUES IN ADDRESSING POPULATION AGING IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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ABSTRACT

The world's contemporary demographic statistics are undergoing significant transformations, primarily characterized by an observable escalation in the population of elderly individuals. This phenomenon of demographic aging has emerged as one of the most substantial social transformations of the 21st century, contributing its effects to almost all sectors of society.

The impact of demographic aging is palpable in labor and financial markets and in the demand for goods and services, including housing, transportation, and social protection. Additionally, demographic aging has considerable implications for the structure and functioning of families. Consequently, it is imperative to address the extant issues related to population aging and keep up with the trends in digitalization.

This study aims to evaluate the current situation and identify the point of intersection between these issues.

Keywords: Aging, older people, older persons, digitalization.

According to the United Nations, the global population aged 60 and over is expected to reach 2.1 billion by 2050, more than double the figure in 2019 [1].

The number of people in the age group of 65 years and older is growing at a high rate compared to other age groups.

According to the report "World Demographic Prospects: Revised Edition 2019", by 2050, every sixth person in the world will be over 65 years old (16% of the population), compared with every 11th in 2019 (9% of the population). By 2050, the age of every fourth person in Europe and North America will fall into the category of people 65 years and older. In 2018, for the first time in history, the number of people aged 65 and older exceeded the number of children under five worldwide. According to forecasts, the number of people aged 80 and older will triple: from 143 million in 2019 to 426 million in 2050 [2].

This aging trend is more common in developed countries but is also a growing concern in developing countries due to improved health and living standards [3].

This concern is related to the need of the elderly population for extensive and specialized medical services due to age-related chronic diseases leading to a sharp increase in healthcare costs. Studies have shown that healthcare costs increase significantly with age,

and older people tend to use medical services more often. Consequently, Governments and healthcare providers face the challenge of allocating a larger share of their budgets to care for older people, diverting resources from other sectors [4].

European countries and the USA frequently use the services of nursing homes. The demand for these services is expected to increase significantly, which will create an additional burden on the healthcare system [5-6].

The economic growth and stability of the country are created at the expense of the able-bodied (economically active) part of the population. An increase in the number of older adults changes the coefficient of economic dependence, which measures the number of working-age people compared to dependents (children and older people). A higher dependency ratio can pressure the economy since fewer working-age people must support more older adults, which can decrease economic productivity [7].

Depending on the country's pension system, the Government should allocate resources to finance pensions and social security programs for age groups. These costs put pressure on public finances and may require tax adjustments or an increase in the retirement age [8].

There is also a tendency in developed countries for people of retirement and pre-retirement age to retire later, which reduces employment opportunities for the younger generation.

This can lead to youth unemployment and potential social unrest [9].

The situation in Kazakhstan

The combination of a decrease in the birth rate and an increase in life expectancy has led to a noticeable increase in the elderly population. According to the Statistics Committee of Kazakhstan, the proportion of the population aged 60 years and older has steadily increased from 7.7% in 2010 to 9.8% in 2020 (Statistics

Committee of Kazakhstan, 2021). This shift is expected to continue as the country develops [10].

According to the Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms, a stable increase in the population is recorded in the Republic of Kazakhstan. At the beginning of 2023, the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan was 19.77 million. The analysis of changes in the gender and age structure of the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan over the past 14 years showed that the total population in the Republic of Kazakhstan increased by 23.68% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The total population in the Republic of Kazakhstan over the past 14 years

The most significant increase in the population over the past ten years has occurred in the cities of republican significance in Almaty (+46.6%) and Astana (+74.1%), which is the result of urbanization. In Mangystau (35.1%), Atyrau (24.8%), Turkestan (23.6%), and Aktobe (16.6%) regions, a high increase in population was also recorded. A minor increase in population

was registered in Kyzylorda (14.7%), Zhambyl (13.9%), Almaty (13.2%), West Kazakhstan (11.4%), Akmola (7.5%), Pavlodar region (0.8%) and a decrease in the number of population was detected in Kostanay (-5.4%), North Kazakhstan (-7.9%), East Kazakhstan (-3.8%), Karaganda region (-0.5%) over the past ten years (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Population changes in regions and large cities in 2023 compared to 2013. % (*the comparison was carried out by the territories of the regions in 2013.)

People at retirement age increased by 67.38% (men by 75.58%, women - by 62.65%) in 2023 compared to 2009 (Figure 3-4).

Figure 3. Change in the number of people 62 years and older in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Figure 4. Population in the Republic of Kazakhstan of retirement age, distribution by sex (62 years and older) over the past 14 years

According to the demographic pyramid and birth rate, there is a dynamic of predominance of the young and economically active population. (Figure 5-6).

Figure 5. Demographic pyramid of Kazakhstan for 2023. (% of the total population)

Figure 6. Fertility rate in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Per 1000 people

There was an increase (by 9.03%) in the economically active stratum (18–62-year-olds) of the population, but the percentage is much less than the older people (67.38%) over the past 14 years (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The number of economically active population in the Republic of Kazakhstan (18–62-year-olds) over the past 14 years

In 1959, the percentage of the population of retirement age in the Republic of Kazakhstan was 5.52%. Since the independence of the Republic of Kazakhstan, this ratio has only been growing, and at the moment it is 8.08%. According to the UN Population Division of the Department of Economic and Social Affairs, the projected ratio of people of retirement age in 2050 will be 11.75% (Figure 8) [11].

Figure 8. The percentage of older adults (65 years and older) in the Republic of Kazakhstan from 1959 to 2023 and the forecast until 2050

Although Kazakhstan has had a high birth rate since 2000, the global trend of increasing the ratio of people of retirement age has not bypassed Kazakhstan.

Conclusions and discussion

Thus, the issues of population aging in Kazakhstan correlate with the literature data and remain relevant for Kazakhstan.

The aging of the population is a consequence of an increase in the quality of life in general and success in public health. The quality of life of older people is becoming increasingly important in assessing and improving the quality and distribution of medical and social services worldwide. According to international experts, due to the progressive aging of the population, the need for care services for older adults living at home will increase several times. This means that more and more older adults will age at home, and most will have one or more chronic diseases, burdening the social security and healthcare system. At the same time, social and healthcare providers are facing care reforms, budget cuts, and stricter regulations at the national and local funding levels. Nevertheless, maintaining the quality of life is one of the most critical outcomes of older people's care services. It is an indicator of the country's social development as a whole [12-14].

Digitalization has become an essential tool in healthcare, especially during the outbreak of coronavirus infection, as it offers a convenient and cost-effective way to provide medical services to older adults who may have serious medical needs or have restrictions in movement and transportation, which makes it challenging to get to the office of a healthcare provider [15].

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a significant increase in the volume of outpatient virtual care, which has jeopardized access to medical care for older people with lower levels of digital literacy [16].

There can be many reasons for the unwillingness or inability of people of pre-retirement and retirement age to actively use cellular applications, social networks, and Internet platforms, from a lack of digital literacy and cognitive decline to a lack of motivation and financial resources. It is important to note that these

causes are interrelated, and bridging the digital divide between older people often requires a multifaceted approach that includes digital literacy programs, accessible technologies, and targeted interventions.

The digital development of various industries (healthcare, trade, banking, e-government) has reached an incredible scale worldwide, which has not bypassed Kazakhstan. The 2020 pandemic has shown the importance and usefulness of digital literacy for people of all ages. For example, in Kazakhstan, the work of e-government (egov.kz): submission of applications, receipt of certificates, and re-registration - practically wholly switched to an electronic format that does not require the presence of a person in Public Service Centers. Some certificates are issued only online. For the convenience of educating the population, there are hotline phone 1414, as well as specialists in public service centers located in each Kazakhstan district. Such innovations, for the most part, positively affect the convenience and speed of obtaining documents.

Internet banking and purchases of goods on the Internet, for example, Kaspi.kz, develops cashless payment, increases the speed of receiving services, and is also available to older persons via mobile communication.

Digitalization of healthcare in Kazakhstan took place in stages. The state program "Information Kazakhstan-2020", where the concept of e-health was approved, was continued in the State Program for the Development of Healthcare "Densauilyk" for 2016-2019 [17].

Currently, in Kazakhstan, thanks to modern technologies, centralized registers have been formed that are necessary for the exchange of data on medical care provided. The development of the healthcare integration platform has been completed. The development of information systems has expanded the range of automated public services, reduced paper document flow in medical organizations, and improved the quality of information about medical and pharmaceutical services. However, all these processes simultaneously will not cancel the traditional trip to the polyclinics. Despite the ongoing activities in the digitalization of healthcare in

Kazakhstan, there is very little research on developing telemedicine for older people. As you know, only universal and fair coverage of all segments of the population with affordable medical care can contribute to the country's development as a whole [18].

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